

Review Article

Individuals and nature-conscious investment: A systematic review and future research agenda

Ciara Clohessy^{a,*}, Vasilis Grigoriadis^b, Fergal O'Brien^a, John Garvey^a

^a *Kemmy Business School, University of Limerick, Limerick, Ireland*

^b *Department of Economics, University of Ioannina, 45110, Ioannina, Greece*

ABSTRACT

Despite the inclusion of biodiversity objectives in sustainable finance taxonomies, their consideration in investment decisions remains limited. This review identifies key behavioural, informational and institutional barriers that inhibit the alignment of individual investment actions with their nature-conscious preferences. The literature highlights barriers across several dimensions that result in a misalignment of individuals preferences and actual investment behaviour. These barriers emerge from cognitive biases, financial literacy, information asymmetries and structural constraints such as pension system design and implementation. We identify areas for future research on behavioural interventions, fiduciary responsibility and the integration of biodiversity data in financial labelling and decision-making tools that can advance the integration of nature data in investment decisions.

1. Introduction

Global biodiversity loss presents one of the most pressing challenges of our time, threatening ecological stability and economic resilience. The economic impact of ecosystem degradation is estimated at \$20 trillion per year, with cascading effects on food security, climate regulation and human-wellbeing (Cortanza et al., 2014). These impacts are not experienced equally, and often directly affect local communities in geographies that are remote to the population of decision-makers and capital owners. Economic activity in the EU geographical region has led to an equivalent loss of 582 million hectares of “pristine” natural areas worldwide, comparable to 60% of the European land area (Ceglar et al., 2023). Despite growing recognition of these risks, biodiversity considerations remain marginal in mainstream investment decisions. While sustainable finance taxonomies and disclosure frameworks have begun to incorporate biodiversity objectives, their influence on individual investment behaviour is limited (Allcott et al., 2026; Gerber & Iacona, 2024; Yule et al., 2023). Redirecting private capital toward nature-positive outcomes is therefore critical to achieving global biodiversity targets (EEA, 2025; Royal Society, 2024), however the mechanisms through which individual investors can align their financial choices with these objectives remain poorly understood.

Investment decisions take place within a global financial system that has evolved to become financially efficient, minimising the cost of allocating capital across assets and geographies. Yet, how this capital is deployed in the physical world and its impacts on natural ecosystems is

poorly evidenced within mainstream finance. This gap reflects deeper theoretical distinctions in sustainable finance between investors motivated by financial value and those motivated by ethical or impact-driven values (Starks, 2023). Research demonstrates that these heterogeneous preferences shape investment choices, from downside-risk mitigation among value-oriented investors (Hoepner et al., 2022) to ethical or societal concerns among values-oriented investors (Riedl & Smeets, 2017). Experimental and field-survey evidence further demonstrates that many retail investors willingly endorse sustainability policies despite anticipating financial costs, revealing strong social and pro-social motivations in asset allocation (Bauer et al., 2021; Brodback et al., 2020). This research is advancing a specific avenue of inquiry that fits into the boarder landscape of sustainable finance literature by examining the systemic barriers to nature-conscious investing. The review explores specific challenges individuals face when activating their investment preferences for nature-conscious options that are distinct in the broader category of ‘environmental’ considerations within the Environmental Social and Governance (ESG) label. While there are significant knowledge gaps in how to assess the nature-impacts of an organisation, Millner-Gulland (2022) notes that ‘it’s already possible to have a rough understanding of the impacts that a given organisation is having on nature - positive and negative’. Nature-conscious investment requires data, tools and financial instruments that must capture and communicate the often highly localised and specialist knowledge that relates to biodiversity and ecosystem impacts. In contrast, the Green House Gas (GHG) emissions of corporates are relatively easy to define by sector and

* Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: clohessy.ciara@ul.ie (C. Clohessy), v.grigoriadis@uoi.gr (V. Grigoriadis), fergal.g.obrien@ul.ie (F. O'Brien), john.garvey@ul.ie (J. Garvey).

offer clear criteria that can be embedded in decision protocols. The review extends from the existing literature on investor motivations which has mixed findings on the effects of divestment versus shareholder engagement on corporate behaviour (Gantchev et al., 2022; Teoh et al., 1999; Wilkens et al., 2025). By analysing the literature around the investment decision-process the review provides new insights into how nature-related preferences can be activated and the pathways through which investors can pressure corporates to increase the adoption of nature-conscious business models from currently low levels (Zu Ermgassen et al., 2022).

How individuals participate in the financial system varies significantly. In its most reduced form, participation can be limited to bank account ownership. In contrast, proactive and financially literate individuals can allocate their capital in a way that is deliberate, sophisticated and avails of a suite of financial instruments and institutions. This review introduces the concept of 'nature-consciousness' to convey a potential future state when financial decisions are made by individuals with explicit consideration of biodiversity and ecosystem impacts, whether positive or negative. Individual investors collectively control significant capital flows, accounting for approximately 25% of equity trading volume in the U.S. and 14% of net asset value in European markets (Einhorn et al., 2023; ESMA, 2022a, 2022b). Their capital is invested in sectors that have very direct and measurable impacts on the physical world. For example, US retirement funds invest \$863 billion (19% of market cap) in US fossil fuel companies (Montes, 2024). Sustainable finance has gained prominence with the emergence of Exchange Traded Funds (ETFs) and European Long-Term Investment Funds (ELTIFs)-relatively new instruments that allow individuals to efficiently allocate capital by theme (ETFs) or by duration (ELTIFs). Traditionally these investment choices are determined by an asset's financial characteristics such as return variability and liquidity (Lynch, 2001). The introduction of labels, most prominently the ESG label, seeks to attract investment based on other non-financial criteria, however biodiversity continues to be a peripheral concern within these frameworks (Crifo et al., 2020). Consequently, investors seeking to allocate capital in a way that takes account of the nature impacts of their investments face a unique set of informational, behavioural, and institutional barriers. These barriers differ from those encountered in broader sustainable investing and are critical because they shape the translation of environmental preferences into actual investment behaviour-a misalignment often described as the "green gap" (Merli et al., 2023). This review synthesizes the existing literature to examine the barriers that prevent individual investors from allocating capital toward investments that protect and restore biodiversity and ecosystems. By systematically identifying these obstacles, the review aims to inform future research that can help direct new capital toward biodiversity-enhancing projects and making such investments more accessible. The analysis focuses specifically on the capital allocation decision-one of three sustainable investing mechanisms outlined by Kölbel et al. (2020). By exploring the technological, structural, and behavioural barriers within this process, we assess whether capital allocation can become a more effective lever for influencing corporate decisions. Thus, this review complements broader research in sustainable finance.

Advancements in financial technology have also supported individual participation in financial markets and changed the way retail investors interact with financial instruments. The number of people globally using smartphones to trade securities increased from 36 million in 2017 to 130 million in 2021. In the same period, more than 20% of all trades made by retail investors were executed on a handheld device (Brière & Thomadakis, 2024). Organisational structures, tax incentives, pension systems, technological platforms, and regulatory frameworks all influence how and where capital flows. Within this system, individual saving and investment behaviour is further affected by household income, financial literacy, and cognitive biases (Abdulrasool et al., 2023). These dynamics are particularly important in the context of

nature-conscious investment, where the decision-making environment is often opaque and misaligned with biodiversity goals (Zhu & Carrasco, 2025). Furthermore, individual investors often lack the expertise, influence or tools to access information on the physical impacts of their investments. Despite this however the existing literature overwhelmingly focuses on sustainable investing in general, leaving biodiversity-specific considerations underexplored. The review protocol used in the current study encompasses the broad body of research on sustainable finance to identify behavioural, informational, and institutional barriers to investment. While these studies primarily examine multiple investment objectives that coalesce within the ESG label, the framework used to analyse these papers is designed to elicit critical insights into decision-making processes, existing regulatory frameworks, and investor behaviour that are transferable to nature-conscious investment contexts. Leveraging this evidence base allows us to synthesize existing knowledge and highlight gaps specific to biodiversity outcomes. Furthermore, the review situates these barriers within a global context while acknowledging regional policy frameworks-such as the EU Taxonomy and Sustainable Finance Disclosure Regulation (SFDR) that influence investor behaviour. This dual perspective allows for a nuanced discussion of how regulatory, technological, and behavioural interventions can be tailored to different markets.

Decision-making takes place in a wide variety of settings-some of these settings promote speed and simplification while others involve consultation and deliberation (Carpenter et al., 2017). In each of these settings, the decision is impacted by supporting technologies and regulatory environment. To structure our analysis of the literature, a conceptual framework is adopted and used to identify where policy, organisational forms and technologies play a role in attenuating nature-consciousness in financial decision-making. Pilaj (2017)'s '5A Model of the Sustainable and Responsible Investment (SRI) Decision' provides a decision architecture that is well suited to the current review. The model spans investors decision-making from the point of deciding to save to post-investment monitoring and adjustment. The additional steps (Assess, Advice and Assign) facilitate a thorough analysis of the barriers investors encounter when approaching nature-conscious investments:

This figure adapts the 5A model (Pilaj, 2017) to provide a framework for nature-conscious investment. The inclusion of step 3 'Assess' is required in the context of nature-conscious investments as the predictability of their effectiveness and long-term costs are still limited (EcoShape, 2021). Understanding how individual investors evaluate nature-conscious investments will help financial providers, regulators, and advisors design products that align with investors' risk tolerances (Jansson et al., 2014). In addition, this study addresses the way in which individual investors seek and receive financial 'Advice' about nature-conscious investments. Understanding how investment advice is delivered to individual investors and the mode used to 'Assess' complex impacts on biodiversity and ecosystems is important. Effective advice has the potential to enhance investors awareness of nature-conscious products, better aligning their investment behaviours with their non-financial preferences. Finally, this study will examine choice activation in two parts - 'Activate (6a)' and 'Assign (6b)'. Individuals may have a preference to allocate their capital according to principles that do no significant harm to biodiversity, however the investment action is delegated to an agent (e.g. a pension fund manager) who may not invest in line with these preferences (Jansen et al., 2008).

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: Section 2 provides a brief overview of the identification and inclusion methodology for the literature used. Section 3 gives a systematic overview of the literature included. In Section 4 applies the decision framework visualised in Fig. 1. Section 5 provides an outline for future research in this field.

Fig. 1. Decision framework for nature-conscious investment.

2. Methodology for identifying relevant literature

This systematic review was conducted in accordance with the PRISMA-P guidelines for planning and documenting review methods to ensure transparency and reproducibility (Moher et al., 2015). A detailed protocol outlining review design, search strategy and inclusion criteria was pre-published and is available at SSRN (Clohessy et al., 2025). Below is a summary of the key elements of the methodology.

2.1. Scope and concept

This review focuses on individual investors and their decision-making processes regarding nature-conscious investments. Given the limited literature on biodiversity-specific investing, the review also incorporates studies on sustainable finance more broadly, including ESG and socially responsible investment (SRI), to identify transferable insights on behavioural, informational, and institutional barriers. This approach is necessary because existing evidence on nature-conscious investment is sparse, and broader sustainable finance research provides a foundation for understanding common decision-making constraints (Gutsche & Ziegler, 2019; Yucel et al., 2023).

2.2. Search strategy

The literature search was designed to be comprehensive and systematic. The PICO framework (Schardt, et al., 2007) was used to distil the primary research question into four key components: Problem (How to promote greater investment in nature-based solutions & biodiversity), Intervention (Motivating retail/individual investors by activating their behavioural tendencies), Control (The primary markets/instruments within which individual investors currently operate) and Outcomes (Behavioural biases/bottlenecks). Key words associated with each element were then used to form the search string. A full list of these keywords can be found in the pre-published protocol (Clohessy et al., 2025) and in the appendix to this paper below. The key words were then combined using the Boolean operators “OR” and “AND” to extract literature that combines all terms for each of the key components of the research question as follows:

Search String = “Problem₁” OR “Problem₂” OR ... “Problem_n” AND “Intervention₁” OR “Intervention₂” OR ... “Intervention_n” AND “Control₁” OR “Control₂” OR ... “Control_n” AND “Outcome₁” OR “Outcome₂” OR ... “Outcome_n”

Searches were conducted on two databases- Scopus and Web of

Science. Google Scholar was also used to search for both academic and grey literature.

2.3. Literature screening

As a result of the database search a total of 1501 titles were exported to excel before removing duplicates (117 studies). At the first stage of screening, studies were assessed on a title and abstract level. Each item was reviewed in line with the PICO criteria, based on its relevance to key components of the research question (for the complete list, please see Clohessy et al., 2025 and in the appendix attached to paper below). The scores for each of the four PICO elements were equally weighted in the inclusion/exclusion decision with each element assigned a value between 0 and 1 depending on the reviewer’s assessment of the text’s relevancy to this study, with a maximum possible score of 4. To address potential bias a second review was carried out following the same methodology, and disagreements between the reviewers were deferred to a third reviewer for a final decision. This method of review was developed to minimise bias and ensure the final literature selected remained relevant to the research question. Studies that scored 3.5 or higher (77 studies) were selected for review. 176 studies were contested by the first two reviewers, and these underwent a second assessment at a lower inclusion threshold of 3 to ensure that borderline papers were not erroneously omitted. From this sample, 121 were then excluded and 55 were reviewed by a third reviewer leading to the exclusion of a further 24 studies and resulting in a total of 108 selected studies (see Fig. 2).

This figure provides an overview of the inclusion/exclusion decision making process for the literature collected via database and registry searches.

3. Results & discussion

3.1. Context

Of the 108 studies included in the review, 91 are journal articles. Among these, finance papers represent 39.6% of the sample, while contributions from environmental science, economics, law, and psychology journals are also present (Table 1). This interdisciplinary requirement is perhaps unsurprising and is linked to findings from conservation efforts in recent decades. Gerber and Iacona (2024) emphasise that aligning data with decision-making processes is crucial for effective biodiversity conservation, highlighting that interdisciplinary and system-wide approaches are essential to ensuring sustainable outcomes. By including literature from different disciplines this

Fig. 2. Literature identification and screening process for systematic review.

Table 1

Journal discipline.

Journal Discipline	Number of Papers	(%)
<i>Social Sciences</i>		
Finance	36	39.60%
Finance	21	23.1%
Sustainable Finance	9	9.9%
Behavioural Finance	6	6.6%
Business Studies	16	17.6%
Business Ethics	4	4.4%
Business & Sustainability	3	3.3%
Business	2	2.2%
Business & Economics	2	2.2%
Business & Technology	1	1.1%
Knowledge & Innovation	1	1.1%
Marketing	1	1.1%
Organisational Change	1	1.1%
Corporate Governance	1	1.1%
Economics	10	11.0%
Economics	7	7.7%
Behavioural Economics	1	1.1%
Energy Economics	1	1.1%
Insurance Economics	1	1.1%
Legal	5	5.5%
Psychology	2	2.2%
Psychology	1	1.1%
Consumer Behaviour	1	1.1%
Social Science	2	2.2%
Ethnography	1	1.1%
<i>Science</i>		
Environmental Science	15	16%
Environment & Sustainability	13	14.3%
Environmental Science	1	1.1%
Sustainable Development	1	1.1%
Science	4	4.4%
Total	91	100%

study provides an overview that is not only scientifically sound, but also considers social, economic and legal impacts for nature-conscious investment.

This table gives a breakdown of the literature included in this study by the discipline of the journal in which they were published.

90% of the existing literature examines the factors influencing

investment patterns in the broader context of sustainable finance while less than 1% explore decision-making in relation to biodiversity linked assets (Table 2). While nature-conscious finance has yet to fully emerge, our approach to this review allows us to synthesise existing knowledge, clustering themes and providing a roadmap of future research as well as the components of the decision-making process that must be addressed.

The geographic distribution of literature examining sustainable investment is interesting as it highlights regional priorities and the focus areas of biodiversity research. It also gives an insight into where investment and conservation efforts are concentrated. According to Figs. 3 and 48% of the papers included in this review are European indicating a strong policy focus on nature-conscious investment in this region.

3.2. Methodologies employed in selected studies

Just over half (53%) of selected studies used questionnaires to gather data, indicating a strong reliance on self-reported data to examine investor decision-making. When a subject area is novel (e.g., green finance, fintech, or ESG investing), researchers lack established theories or comprehensive data. In this context, questionnaires are typically used to identify key themes (e.g., investor attitudes, barriers to adoption), gauge awareness and perceptions and map preliminary trends before deeper analysis (Saunders et al., 2019). In contrast to conventional financial economics, which typically relies on large scale market-based data and regulatory context, emerging fields like green finance deploy questionnaires to collect primary data quickly and to capture subjective factors (e.g., trust in ESG ratings, behavioural biases etc.). Before conducting experimental or econometric analyses, researchers use surveys to test initial assumptions and refine research questions for future studies (Bryman, 2016). The dominance of this method is reflected in the sample of selected studies.

Other methods including choice experiments and conjoint analysis offer more structured approaches to understanding decision-making under hypothetical scenarios (Table 3). These methods are particularly valuable in isolating the trade-offs investors make between financial and non-financial factors when approaching an investment decision (Gutsche & Ziegler, 2019).

Table 2

Investment Type. This table gives an overview of the types of the types of investments discussed in the literature included in this study.

Investment Type	Definition	No. of Titles	(%)
Sustainable Finance	A broad category encompassing financial activities that integrate environmental, social, and general 'green' considerations to support long-term sustainable development.	47	44%
ESG	Investment practices that incorporate environmental, social, and governance criteria to assess corporate performance, often used for risk management and value-oriented decision-making.	28	26%
SRI	Investments that apply explicit ethical, social, or normative screening (e.g., avoiding harmful sectors) in addition to financial considerations.	23	21%
Climate Investment	Investments focused specifically on climate change mitigation or adaptation outcomes, such as emissions reductions or climate resilience.	4	4%
General Finance	Studies addressing financial topics with incidental or indirect sustainability relevance but without a dedicated sustainability focus.	2	2%
Renewable Energy Investment	Investments directed toward renewable technologies (e.g., solar, wind, hydro) that support energy transition and decarbonisation.	2	2%
Land Use	Investments related to land management, conversion, or conservation, often involving agriculture, forestry, or spatial planning.	1	0.50%
Biodiversity Investment	Financial flows designed explicitly to protect, restore, or enhance biodiversity outcomes (e.g., habitat restoration, species protection).	1	0.50%
Total		108	100%

3.3. Thematic overview

While the selected studies address the broader topic of sustainable

finance they provide important insights into financial instruments, structural features of the investment market, such as information asymmetries and also examine behavioural tendencies and governance constraints. Several of the themes identified within these studies have specific effects for investors seeking to allocate capital towards biodiversity and ecosystem outcomes, where data scarcity and methodological inconsistency are particularly acute (Christiansen et al., 2023; Giglio et al., 2023). For example, equities and mutual funds often expose investors to challenges related to inconsistent ESG methodologies and limited nature-related disclosures, whereas green bonds raise issues of taxonomy credibility and the verifiability of use of proceeds claims (Allcott et al., 2026; Bazrafshan, 2023; Riedl & Smeets, 2017). Pension products, by contrast, introduce long-term fiduciary considerations and default-option effects that shape how beneficiaries engage with sustainability information (Faradynawati & Söderberg, 2022; Lofgren & Nordblom, 2024). This motivates the thematic mapping that follows, which integrates these insights across the investment lifecycle to clarify how different factors influence decision-making at each stage.

Table 4 below maps key research themes identified in the literature, such as information quality, behavioural biases, regulation and technology, at each stage of the decision-making lifecycle, as structured by the extended 7A framework. This table allows us to link theoretical constructs established in the existing body of work with practical investor behaviours, offering a clear understanding of how different factors influence decision-making at specific points in the investment process. For example, information quality, availability and processing

Table 3

Methodology. This table gives an overview of the methodologies employed in the literature included in this study.

Methodology	(%)
Survey/Questionnaire	53%
Choice Experiment	11%
Empirical Analysis	11%
Literature Review	9%
Conjoint Analysis	5%
Choice Experiment & Conjoint Analysis	3%
Difference-in-Difference Method	2%
Discussion	2%
Dynamic Stochastic General Equilibrium (DSGE) model	2%
Survey/Questionnaire & Conjoint Analysis	2%
Total	100%

Fig. 3. Geographical Location of Literature. This figure provides an illustration of the geographical distribution of papers included in this study.

Table 4
Investment choice architecture.

		Investment Choice Architecture						
		Activation	Awareness	Assessment	Attitude	Advice	Action (Assignment)	Adjustment
Themes/ Barriers	Behavioural Biases	Katelouzou and Micheler (2022) Syahfi (2023) Gajewski et al. (2023) Khan et al. (2024) Lofgren and Nordblom (2024) Sood et al. (2023)	de Zwaan et al. (2015) Syahfi (2023) Deka et al. (2023) Blomqvist and Stradi (2024)	Munteanu et al. (2007) Bassen et al. (2019) Park and Oh (2022) Rooh et al. (2023) Sood et al. (2023) Khan et al. (2024)	Sultana et al. (2018) Lagerkvist et al. (2020) Chan et al. (2022) Rooh et al. (2023) Deka et al. (2023) Pasquino and Lucarelli (2024) Mishra et al. (2023) Colaert (2024) Khan et al. (2024) Akbar et al. (2024) Azad et al. (2024)	Munteanu et al. (2007); de Zwaan et al. (2015) Apostolakis et al. (2016) Biong and Silkoset (2017) Bassen et al. (2019) Lagerkvist et al. (2020) Faradynawati and Söderberg (2022) Katelouzou and Micheler (2022) Sood et al. (2023)	Munteanu et al. (2007) Bassen et al. (2019) Lagerkvist et al. (2020) Park and Oh (2022) Chan et al. (2022) Sood et al. (2023) Pasquino and Lucarelli (2024) Gevorkova et al. (2024) Gajewski et al. (2023) Khan et al. (2024) Lofgren and Nordblom (2024)	Anderson and Robinson (2019)
	Non-Financial Preferences	Apostolakis et al. (2016) Sultana et al. (2018) Xu et al. (2022) Gevorkova et al. (2024) Merli et al. (2023) Seifert et al. (2024) Lofgren and Nordblom (2024)	Borgers and Pownall (2014) Sultana et al. (2018) Gutsche and Ziegler (2019) Vyas, Mehta, and Sharma (2022) Marshall et al. (2021) Petelczyc (2022) Thanki et al. (2022) Xu et al. (2022) Tang and Teoh (2023) Chen et al. (2023) Blomqvist and Stradi (2024) Robinson & Anderson (2024)	Nilsson (2008) Hafenstein and Bassen (2016) Kakeu (2017) Riedl and Smeets (2017) Sultana et al. (2018) Bourcet and Bovari (2020) Faradynawati and Söderberg (2022) Park and Oh (2022) Xu et al. (2022) Siemroth and Hornuf (2024) Gaspar et al. (2023) Li et al. (2023) Giglio et al. (2023) Christiansen et al. (2023) Lofgren and Nordblom (2024) Sood et al. (2023) Schwertner and Sohn (2024)	Apostolakis et al. (2016) Sultana et al. (2018) Rehanloo et al. (2018) Hammerle et al. (2021) Mavlutova et al. (2022) Rana and Sarva (2023) Cucinelli and Soana (2023) Rooh et al. (2023) Merli et al. (2023) Gevorkova et al. (2024) Yucel et al. (2023) Pasquino and Lucarelli (2024) Gevorkova et al. (2024) Mishra et al. (2023) Seifert et al. (2024) Mullen et al. (2024) Blomqvist and Stradi (2024) Sood et al. (2023)	Jansson et al. (2014) Borgers and Pownall (2014) Steiauf and Schäfer (2014) de Zwaan et al. (2015) Zwergel et al. (2019) Biong and Silkoset (2017) Vyas et al. (2022) Faradynawati and Söderberg (2022) Sood et al. (2023) Raut, Shastri, Mishra, and Tiwari (2023)	Borgers and Pownall (2014) Hafenstein and Bassen (2016) Riedl and Smeets (2017) Gutsche and Ziegler (2019) Brodback et al. (2020) Bourcet and Bovari (2020) Hammerle et al. (2021) Cucinelli and Soana (2023) Siemroth and Hornuf (2023) Gao, Luo, Tian, and Yang (2024) Giglio et al. (2023) Gevorkova et al. (2024) Chen et al. (2023) Christiansen et al. (2023) Lofgren and Nordblom (2024) Wang et al. (2024) Rakotomavo (2011) ESMA (2022a, 2022b) Becker et al. (2022) Bazrafshan (2023) Janz et al. (2023) Lofgren and Nordblom (2024) Assaf et al. (2024) Benuzzi et al. (2024) Schwertner and Sohn (2024)	Anderson and Robinson (2019) Xu et al. (2022) Mavlutova et al. (2022) Tang and Teoh (2023) Murashima (2023) Robinson & Anderson (2024) Schwertner and Sohn (2024)
	Information (Quality, Availability)	Syahfi (2023) Khan et al. (2024)	de Zwaan et al. (2015) Gutsche et al. (2021) Park and Oh (2022) Syahfi (2023) Becker et al. (2022) ESMA (2022a, 2022b) Maso (2023) Lofgren and Nordblom (2024) Akbar et al. (2024) Filippini et al. (2024) Wang et al. (2024) Sood et al. (2023)	Hafenstein and Bassen (2016) Bassen et al. (2019) Bourcet and Bovari (2020) Gutsche et al. (2021) Park and Oh (2022) ESMA (2022a, 2022b) Bazrafshan (2023) Janz et al. (2023) Liu and Wan (2023) Sood et al. (2023) Mullen et al. (2024) Assaf et al. (2024)	Hafenstein and Bassen (2016) Bourcet and Bovari (2020) Gutsche et al. (2021) Straub et al. (2023) Li et al. (2023) Mullen et al. (2024) Assaf et al. (2024) Lukas (2024)	Haigh and Shapiro (2013) Bassen et al. (2019) Colaert (2024) ESMA (2022a, 2022b) Faradynawati and Söderberg (2022) Assaf et al. (2024) Horn (2024)	Janz et al. (2023) Schwertner and Sohn (2024)	

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Table 4 (continued)

	Investment Choice Architecture								
	Activation	Awareness	Assessment	Attitude	Advice	Action (Assignment)	Adjustment		
Policy/Regulation	Benijts (2009) Katelouzou and Micheler (2022) Burghof et al. (2021) Lofgren and Nordblom (2024)	Marszk and Lechman (2024)	Horn (2024)						
		Steiauf and Schäfer (2014)	Benuzzi et al. (2024)	Benijts (2009)	Steiauf and Schäfer (2014)	Haigh and Shapiro (2013)	Benijts (2009)	Murashima (2023)	
		Prajapati et al. (2021)	Biong and Silkoset (2017)	Bourcet and Bovari (2020)	Gutsche and Ziegler (2019)	Jansson et al. (2014)	Apostolakis et al. (2016)	Rehman et al. (2024)	
		Colaert (2024)	Sultana et al. (2018)	Hammerle et al. (2021)	Gutsche and Ziegler (2019)	Steiauf and Schäfer (2014)	Sultana et al. (2018)		
		Zadek et al. (2021)	Bourcet and Bovari (2020)	Prajapati et al. (2021)	Bourcet and Bovari (2020)	Apostolakis et al. (2016)	Katelouzou and Micheler (2022)		
		Faradynawati and Söderberg (2022)	Hammerle et al. (2021)	Bazrafshan (2023)	Bourcet and Bovari (2020)	Diouf et al. (2016)	Micheler (2022)		
		Petelczyc (2022)	Prajapati et al. (2021)		Bourcet and Bovari (2020)	Burghof et al. (2021)	Prajapati et al. (2021)		
		Li et al. (2023)	Bazrafshan (2023)		Petelczyc (2022)	Gutsche et al. (2021)	Zadek et al. (2021)		
		Tang and Teoh (2023)			Chan et al. (2022)	Colaert (2024)	Becker et al. (2022)		
		Maso (2023)			Straub et al. (2023)	Faradynawati and Söderberg (2022)	Murashima (2023)		
		Filippini et al. (2024)			Rana and Sarva (2023)	Katelouzou and Micheler (2022)	Gajewski et al. (2023)		
		Wang et al. (2024)			Colaert (2024)	Katelouzou and Micheler (2022)	Lofgren and Nordblom (2024)		
		Azad et al. (2024)			Gatzert and Kraus (2024)	Pasquino and Lucarelli (2024)	Inderst and Opp (2024)		
		Horn (2024)			Azad et al. (2024)	Lofgren and Nordblom (2024)	Marszk and Lechman (2024)		
		Financial Literacy	Syahfi (2023) Merli et al. (2023) Yucel et al. (2023) Seifert et al. (2024) Lofgren and Nordblom (2024)	Gutsche et al. (2021)	Borgers and Pownall (2014)	Rehanloo et al. (2018)	Borgers and Pownall (2014)	Borgers and Pownall (2014)	Mavlutova et al. (2020)
Mehta, Singh, Mittal, and Singla (2021)	Hafenstein and Bassen (2016)			D'Hondt et al. (2022)	Biong and Silkoset (2017)	D'Hondt et al. (2022)	Janz et al. (2023)		
Cucinelli and Soana (2023)	Syahfi (2023)			Merli et al. (2023)	Seifert et al. (2024)	Faradynawati and Söderberg (2022)	Cucinelli and Soana (2023)	Seifert et al. (2024)	
Yucel et al. (2023)	D'Hondt et al. (2022)			Yucel et al. (2023)	Seifert et al. (2024)		Yucel et al. (2023)	Robinson & Anderson (2024)	
Seifert et al. (2024)	Adhiyogo et al. (2022)			Azad et al. (2024)	Merli et al. (2023)		Janz et al. (2023)		
Akbar et al. (2024)	Merli et al. (2023)				Merli et al. (2023)		Seifert et al. (2024)		
Filippini et al. (2024)	Seifert et al. (2024)				Azad et al. (2024)		Akbar et al. (2024)		
Azad et al. (2024)	Filippini et al. (2024)								
Au et al. (2021)	Faradynawati and Söderberg (2022)			Faradynawati and Söderberg (2022)	Faradynawati and Söderberg (2022)	Burghof et al. (2021)	Au et al. (2021)	Macchiavello and Siri (2020)	
Macchiavello and Siri (2020)	Faradynawati and Söderberg (2022)			Macchiavello & Siri (2020)	Pasquino and Lucarelli (2024)	Au et al. (2021)	Faradynawati and Söderberg (2022)		
Technology	Chen and Volz (2022) Faradynawati and Söderberg (2022) Siemroth and Hornuf (2023) Merli et al. (2023) Pasquino and Lucarelli (2024)	An et al. (2022)	Merli et al. (2023)	Merli et al. (2023)	Chen and Volz (2022)	An et al. (2022)			
		Macchiavello and Siri (2020)	Merli et al. (2023)	Merli et al. (2023)	Faradynawati and Söderberg (2022)	Chen and Volz (2022)			
		Faradynawati and Söderberg (2022)	Merli et al. (2023)	Merli et al. (2023)	Faradynawati and Söderberg (2022)	Faradynawati and Söderberg (2022)	Siemroth and Hornuf (2023)		
		Siemroth and Hornuf (2023)	Merli et al. (2023)	Merli et al. (2023)	Faradynawati and Söderberg (2022)	Faradynawati and Söderberg (2022)	Siemroth and Hornuf (2023)		
		Merli et al. (2023)	Merli et al. (2023)	Merli et al. (2023)	Faradynawati and Söderberg (2022)	Faradynawati and Söderberg (2022)	Marszk and Lechman (2024)		
		Pasquino and Lucarelli (2024)	Merli et al. (2023)	Merli et al. (2023)	Faradynawati and Söderberg (2022)	Faradynawati and Söderberg (2022)	Marszk and Lechman (2024)		
		Profit Maximisation (Risk/Return)	Sultana et al. (2018) Merli et al. (2023) Lofgren and Nordblom (2024) Gatzert and Kraus (2024) Yucel et al. (2023) Raut et al. (2023)	Gutsche and Ziegler (2019)	Nilsson (2008)	Jansson et al. (2014)	Apostolakis et al. (2016)	Nilsson (2008)	Murashima (2023)
				Marshall et al. (2021)	Rakotomavo (2011)	Diouf et al. (2016)	Biong and Silkoset (2017)	Riedl and Smeets (2017)	Xu et al. (2022)
				Au et al. (2021)	Jansson et al. (2014)	Lagerkvist et al. (2020)	Vyas et al. (2022)	(2017)	Murashima (2023)
				Thanki et al. (2022)	Apostolakis et al. (2016)	D'Hondt et al. (2022)	Faradynawati and Söderberg (2022)	Brodbeck et al. (2020)	
Yucel et al. (2023)	(2016)			Rana and Sarva (2023)	Söderberg (2022)	Lagerkvist et al. (2020)			
Horn (2024)	Kakeu (2017)			Rooh et al. (2023)	Katelouzou and Micheler (2022)	Vyas et al. (2022)			
Marszk and Lechman (2024)	Rehanloo et al. (2018)			Siemroth and Hornuf (2023)	Katelouzou and Micheler (2022)	Petelczyc (2022)			
	Gutsche and Ziegler (2019)			Gutsche and Ziegler (2019)	Horn (2024)	D'Hondt et al. (2022)			
	Bourcet and Bovari (2020)			Bourcet and Bovari (2020)	Horn (2024)	Adhiyogo et al. (2022)			
	Panja and Das (2022)			Panja and Das (2022)	Deka et al. (2023)	Thanki et al. (2022)			
			Yucel et al. (2023)	Murashima (2023)					
			Pasquino and Lucarelli (2024)	Duranay and Özsoy					

(continued on next page)

Table 4 (continued)

Investment Choice Architecture						
Activation	Awareness	Assessment	Attitude	Advice	Action (Assignment)	Adjustment
		Marshall et al. (2021) Park and Oh (2022) Duranay and Özsoy (2023) Stenroth and Hornuf (2023) Gaspar et al. (2023) Lofgren and Nordblom (2024) Horn (2024)	Giglio et al. (2023) Lofgren and Nordblom (2024) Gatzert and Kraus (2024) Blomqvist and Stradi (2024)		(2023) Stenroth and Hornuf (2023) Blomqvist and Stradi (2024) Raut et al. (2023) Marszk and Lechman (2024)	
Communication	de Zwaan et al. (2015) Marshall et al. (2015) Prajapati et al. (2021) Syahfi (2023) Becker et al. (2022) ESMA (2022a, 2022b) Gaspar et al. (2023) Maso (2023) Lofgren and Nordblom (2024) Sood et al. (2023) Horn (2024)	Bassen et al. (2019) Prajapati et al. (2021) ESMA (2022a, 2022b) Bazrafshan (2023)	de Zwaan et al. (2015) Gutsche and Ziegler (2019) Lagerkvist et al. (2020) Gutsche et al. (2021) Straub et al. (2023) Pasquino and Lucarelli (2024) Lofgren and Nordblom (2024)	de Zwaan et al. (2015) Diouf et al. (2016) Vyas et al. (2022) Faradynawati and Söderberg (2022) ESMA (2022a, 2022b) Rooth et al. (2023) Pasquino and Lucarelli (2024) Sood et al. (2023) Horn (2024)	Lagerkvist et al. (2020) ESMA (2022a, 2022b) Becker et al. (2022) Bazrafshan (2023) Lofgren and Nordblom (2024) Schwertner and Sohn (2024)	Straub et al. (2023) Schwertner and Sohn (2024)

ability has an impact at every stage of an individual investment allocation process highlighting the central role of information asymmetries and cognitive load in shaping investor outcomes (Bassen et al., 2019). In contrast studies exploring behavioural biases, such as inertia or status quo bias, are more concentrated around investment action and assignment, where decisions are either initiated or delegated (Lofgren & Nordblom, 2024).

By structuring the existing theory in this way, the table exposes under-researched intersections, such as post-investment adjustments, and provides a roadmap for future research to target specific gaps in the literature.

This table maps key research themes identified in the literature at each stage of the decision-making process.

4. Investment choice architecture

4.1. Investment activation

Investment activation is the first step of the investment choice architecture and refers to the decision of individuals to commence saving or investing, and where applicable to accept or set a default contribution rate (Pilaj, 2017). At this stage the focus is on participation and initiation decisions rather than on product selection or portfolio rebalancing, which are addressed in later stages.

The literature on activating saving and investment choices is extensive and encompasses neoclassical and behavioural schools of economic thought (Apostolakis et al., 2016; Gajewski et al., 2023; Katelouzou & Micheler, 2022). Neoclassical accounts model the individual as an optimiser who initiates investing when lifetime utility (given risk and return characteristics) warrants participation. In contrast, behavioural finance shows that activation is highly sensitive to frictions and heuristics such as inertia or status-quo bias that prevent or delay enrolment or contribution setting (Gajewski et al., 2023; Thaler & Benartzi, 2004).

These biases are reinforced by a financial system that seeks to simplify choice and aggregate capital flows. For example, institutions for occupational retirement provision (IORPs) in Europe manage c.€2.7 trillion of assets for 71.6 million beneficiaries (EIOPA, 2024). The requirement to move a large volume of capital often reduces opportunity for choice, resulting in inconsistencies between individuals' preferences and actual investment behaviour (Apostolakis et al., 2016).

Financial literacy, the ability to process core financial information, filter noise and engage with financial products, supports participation. Conversely, low literacy and cognitive overload increase reliance on heuristics and inaction (Seifert et al., 2024; Yucel et al., 2023). However, cognitive biases, such as default option bias, confirmation bias and overconfidence, can hinder decision-making especially when decisions require the inclusion of non-financial or sustainability preferences (Katelouzou & Micheler, 2022; Khan et al., 2024; Lofgren & Nordblom, 2024). For nature-conscious investors, this gap between intention and action is often due to financial illiteracy especially when faced with complex biodiversity data.

Policy instruments such as auto-enrolment schemes have emerged as a response to under-saving and provide potential pathways for redirecting financial flows towards nature-conscious projects. Madrian and Shea (2001), cited in Gajewski et al. (2023), found that auto-enrolment in U.S. 401(k) plans significantly increased retirement savings participation, with most individuals sticking to the default contribution rate and managed funds. Similarly, the National Employment Savings Trust (NEST) rolled out by the UK Government in 2010 facilitates auto-enrolment in UK pension schemes (Katelouzou & Micheler, 2022). National policy objectives such as nature restoration targets could be embedded in the design of auto-enrolment programmes by prioritising green bonds that focus on nature-conscious investments by sovereign and municipal issuers. Recent recommendations for pension reform draw attention to the promise of this approach to activating private financial flows towards national priorities (Ministry of Housing

Communities & Local Government, 2025).

Complementary enablers such as targeted fiscal incentives (tax reliefs), and financial instruments, (sovereign green bonds), can reduce some of the barriers individuals face when deciding to invest in environmental projects (Benijts, 2009; Paul et al., 2021). Greater synergy between regulation and technology for example simplified onboarding, clear prompts and user-centric defaults on digital platforms, have fostered more prudent saving behaviours among individual investors (Burghof et al., 2021; Macchiavello & Siri, 2020). Digital tools like green banking platforms and robo-advisors can help reduce friction at the activation stage by streamlining enrolment, tailoring advice and mitigating psychological biases through machine learning (Faradynawati & Söderberg, 2022; Merli et al., 2023; Pašiušienė et al., 2023). The integration of regulatory frameworks with technological solutions can further safeguard investors, ensuring a stable environment within which individuals can be encouraged to allocate their capital towards nature-conscious investments (Burghof et al., 2021).

4.2. Investment choice awareness

Investment choice awareness is the extent to which investors know that nature-conscious investment options exist and understand how these differ from conventional financial products. Awareness is important as even environmentally motivated individuals cannot choose nature-conscious products if they are not aware of their existence (Pilaj, 2017).

Studies examining investor awareness highlight a persistent disconnect between general concern for environmental issues and recognition of appropriate financial instruments. While many individuals express worry about climate change or biodiversity loss, only a minority link these concerns to specific sustainable investment products (Blomqvist & Stradi, 2024; Sultana et al., 2018). Anderson and Robinson (2024) note, for example, that while geographic proximity to forest fires caused by the 2018 heatwave in Sweden increased awareness of climate change across the population, it did not translate into changes in pension allocation decisions. This gap suggests that awareness of environmental problems does not automatically translate into awareness of investment pathways available to address them.

Regulatory frameworks, such as the Markets in Financial Instruments Directive (MiFID) and the EU Taxonomy are beginning to strengthen awareness of sustainable financial products (Cucinelli & Soana, 2023; ESMA, 2022a, 2022b). These regulations require financial advisors to ask clients about their sustainability preferences, enhancing the visibility of such products among individual investors (European Commission, 2021; European Parliament and Council, 2014, 2016).

While this paper discusses the effect of financial advice on investor decision-making in more detail (see section 4.5) it's important to note how this regulatory shift increases awareness of sustainable products among investors who would not otherwise encounter them. Pension trustees and financial advisors serve as critical points of contact for individual investors, ensuring that preferences are reflected in investment decisions (Apostolakis et al., 2016; Jansson et al., 2014). Evidence from pension settings shows that passive investors rarely seek information independently, leaving the framing and presentation of options by institutions as primary drivers of awareness (Anderson & Robinson, 2019; Gutsche & Ziegler, 2019). In such contexts, awareness depends less on investor initiative and more on institutional communication. This dynamic is particularly important for nature-conscious investment, where product availability remains limited, terminology is less familiar to the public, and biodiversity benefits are harder for individuals to interpret without guidance. Therefore, insights from the broader sustainable-finance literature apply directly: if investors struggle to recognise well-established climate or ESG products, the awareness barrier is even more pronounced for emerging nature-conscious instruments.

Educational efforts and basic financial literacy also influence

awareness. Yucel et al. (2023) identify the role financial institutions can play in improving client awareness on sustainable finance options by conducting workshops and promotional campaigns to highlight the financial aspects of sustainable products, such as risk, return and diversification properties. This approach aims to educate potential investors by increasing sustainable finance literacy and fostering a favourable disposition towards sustainable finance instruments. The ongoing regulatory push in this direction complements broader efforts to address persistent shortcomings in awareness for sustainable finance, where environmentally conscious individuals often lack the knowledge or tools to unlock their preferences (Lofgren & Nordblom, 2024). Effective communication by advisors, regulators and governments is essential to raise awareness as many pension holders do not know how their funds are invested due to disengagement or information overload (deZwaan et al., 2015). As nature-conscious investment products evolve, these findings provide a strong foundation for understanding how awareness can be cultivated and why targeted education is essential for overcoming the even larger visibility gap facing biodiversity-linked finance.

Finally, several international initiatives seek to raise broad awareness of nature-conscious finance opportunities. Organisations such as the Finance for Biodiversity Foundation promotes nature-related risk disclosures and open biodiversity data (FfB, 2024), the OECD is supporting biodiversity-positive incentives like ecosystem service payments and biodiversity-relevant tax exemptions (OECD, 2024) and the International Finance Corporation (IFC) has introduced biodiversity finance metrics to align investments with the Global Biodiversity Framework (IFC, 2024). These efforts, while not aimed directly at retail investors, contribute to a broader information environment that supports growing awareness of nature-conscious finance over time.

4.3. Investment assessment

Investment decisions are not solely driven by rational evaluations of risk and return but are also shaped by behavioural, psychological and informational factors resulting in less-optimal choices (Filippini et al., 2024; Khan et al., 2024; Rooh et al., 2023; Siemroth & Hornuf, 2023; Sood et al., 2023). Investment assessment refers to the process by which individuals evaluate the characteristics of an asset in order to inform and justify their investment decisions. At this point, investors have moved beyond basic awareness and begin weighing risks, returns, costs and sustainability attributes.

Emotional drivers also play a role, as those with strong environmental values or a sense of “warm glow” are more willing to sacrifice returns for sustainability (Gutsche et al., 2021) while feelings of guilt can increase openness to trade-offs (Gevorkova et al., 2024). In Sweden, although 49% of investors in the pension market agreed that fund managers should integrate sustainable assets into their portfolios, irrespective of the potential for higher returns, nearly 70% of respondents emphasized the importance of securing the safety of their future returns (Jansson et al., 2014). Understanding individuals mixed priorities is especially relevant for nature-conscious investments, where perceived risks are frequently higher and expected returns more uncertain.

Empirical evidence also highlights the dominant role of traditional financial information during the assessment stage. In a large online choice-experiment across six European countries Bassen et al. (2019) note that information about risks, costs, and performance significantly impacts investors' assessment of a climate-related investment. They varied the presentation format of climate information and analysed the relative importance of different attributes in investment decisions, finding that traditional financial information (risk, costs, and performance) accounted for approximately 73% of the decision-making process. While including sustainability information in their assessment allows individuals to feel more connected to a potential investment decision, by aligning financial choices with personal values and long-term impact, it still plays a secondary role in decision-making

(Hafenstein & Bassen, 2016). The same pattern is expected to hold for nature-conscious financial products: although biodiversity outcomes may motivate certain investors more strongly, most will still primarily evaluate these products through the lens of financial risk and return.

Although ESG labelling is widely used to simplify investment assessments, its effectiveness is undermined by inconsistent standards and a lack of transparency, which can mislead investors rather than help them align their choices with their sustainability goals (Becker et al., 2022). Current practices often fall short of providing the reliability and comparability needed for truly informed decision-making. By conducting a choice experiment, where participants were presented with binary choices between companies associated with different ESG dimensions, Benuzzi et al. (2024) found that individuals prioritising sustainability tended to focus on the E-pillar of ESG labels (Environment) whereas those who prioritised financial performance focused on the S-pillar (Social), which they perceived as contributing to better financial returns. This highlights that investment assessment depends not only on the information presented but also on investors underlying priorities.

These insights, though derived largely from general sustainable-finance contexts, translate directly to nature-conscious investment assessments. Biodiversity metrics and nature-related disclosures are even less standardised than ESG labels, increasing the risk of confusion and misinterpretation. As a result, investors may struggle to evaluate the impact, dependencies, or financial implications of nature-conscious investments unless information is presented in a clear, comparable, and decision-relevant format. Strengthening the tools investors use to assess nature-conscious assets is therefore critical for enabling individuals to make informed, preference-aligned choices.

4.4. Investment attitude

Investment choice attitude refers to an individual's predisposition to evaluate and respond to investment options in a particular way, shaped by their beliefs, values, and perceived risks (or benefits) (Pilaj, 2017). These attitudes, distinct from (but somewhat influenced by) the risk-return assessments discussed in section 4.3, play a central role in determining individual's investment intentions.

Recent literature highlights how sustainable investment decisions are shaped by a complex interplay of attitudinal, cognitive and emotional factors that extend beyond traditional financial metrics. Studies show that pro-environmental values (Apostolakis et al., 2016; Azad et al., 2024), ethical motivations (Mullen et al., 2024) and psychological biases, such as loss aversion and overconfidence (Rooh et al., 2023) play a central role in shaping individual investors preferences and subsequent behaviours. For nature-conscious investment specifically, these attitudinal mechanisms are especially salient: biodiversity impacts are often less visible and harder to quantify than sustainability outcomes, meaning investors rely more heavily on values, trust, and subjective perceptions when forming attitudes toward nature-conscious products.

Empirical studies confirm the importance of environmental attitudes in shaping sustainable investment intentions. Apostolakis et al. (2016) use the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) to show that pro-environmental views significantly increase the likelihood of investing in ESG-aligned products. Their survey of Dutch pension participants reveals that individuals who hold strong environmental attitudes exhibited a high willingness to pay (i.e., forgo higher returns) to invest in such products. Similarly, Rana and Sarva (2023) find that attitude plays a significant mediating role between various non-financial factors influencing the intentions of individual investors. Environmental concerns positively shape investors' attitudes, leading them to divest from environmentally harmful assets and invest in sustainable financial instruments, even at a premium (Azad et al., 2024). 97.7% of investors in community energy initiatives in the UK cited environmental concerns as their principal influence, highlighting the power of ethical attitudes on investment choice (Mullen et al., 2024). This underscores the

complex relationship between intentions and financial objectives and the need for a nuanced approach to investment that balances moral considerations with economic outcomes (Lagerkvist et al., 2020). These findings, although largely emerging from climate and ESG-related contexts, apply directly to nature-conscious investment as biodiversity products similarly appeal to altruism, pro-nature values, and moral identity.

Generational and contextual factors also shape attitudes. Individual investors with a positive perception of the environmental impact of sustainable finance instruments are more likely to develop favourable investment attitudes towards these instruments (Yucel et al., 2023). Conversely, younger investors tend to hold stronger pro-environmental attitudes yet are often conflicted by the appeal of short-term financial gains—a tension that weakens the link between their attitudes and their actions (Pašiušienė et al., 2023). This tension is likely even more pronounced for nature-conscious investments, where financial returns are often perceived as uncertain or long-term, making positive attitudes more fragile.

Cognitive biases such as affinity bias, the gambler's fallacy, herding behaviour, loss aversion, and overconfidence play a crucial role in shaping individual investors' attitudes when making investment decisions. Rooh et al. (2023) collected data from 421 individual investors in the Pakistani stock market using a questionnaire to understand how these biases impacted investment decision-making, the results of which are summarised in Table 5 below. These biases are highly relevant for nature-conscious investment, where uncertainty around outcomes can amplify loss aversion, and unfamiliarity can increase reliance on heuristics or herding behaviour.:

This table gives an overview of cognitive biases and how they impact investment decisions as discussed in Rooh et al. (2023).

Clear, accessible information can counteract behavioural biases by improving understanding, reducing uncertainty and strengthening positive attitudes. Regulations like the EU's Sustainable Finance Disclosure Regulation (SFDR) support this by enhancing communication and making complex sustainability data more accessible to investors. Assaf et al. (2024) surveyed a sample of French retail investors to understand the importance they place on different ESG criteria. They performed correlation analysis on this data to understand the relationship between ESG scoring and firm valuation and found higher ESG scores were associated with lower risk, reinforcing the utility of ESG metrics in shaping investors attitudes. Although these findings emerge from broader ESG contexts, they are directly relevant for nature-conscious investment, where improved disclosure of biodiversity impacts is likely to strengthen positive investor perceptions. Clear and transparent labelling fosters trust and promotes more positive attitudes for nature-conscious financial products among individual investors.

Understanding what affects investors' attitudes toward nature-conscious investments is essential for promoting more sustainable financial choices and aligning capital flows with environmental goals.

Table 5
Cognitive biases in investment decision-making.

Affinity Bias	Investors with strong environmental values prefer companies that align with their preferences investing in companies with strong ESG credentials, even if they do not offer the best financial returns.
Gamblers Fallacy	Investors often believe that past events affect future probabilities believing value will decrease after a period of expansion, despite no rational basis for this belief.
Hearding Behaviour	Investors disregard their personal preferences to follow the actions of others, despite their personal preferences.
Loss Aversion	Investors are averse to loss making, favouring traditional financial instruments over ESG products due to the perceived risk of such investments.
Overconfidence	Overconfident investors believe they can outperform the market, leading them to overestimate their ability to pick successful investments.

This behavioural perspective marks a clear departure from neo-classical economic thought, which assumes rational actors make decisions solely based on risk and return (Yucel et al., 2023) and underscores the need for regulatory and informational frameworks that support favourable attitudes towards nature-conscious investments (Becker et al., 2022). Investor attitude plays a crucial role in decision-making by shaping how potential investments are perceived. These attitudes may also influence whether they seek financial advice, with more cautious investors more likely consult professionals before committing funds.

4.5. Investment advice

Individual investors often lack the expertise or confidence to make optimal investment choices independently, prompting them to seek professional guidance. Limited experience and behavioural biases drive demand for professional advice (Colaert, 2024; Rooh et al., 2023), while policy instruments like auto-enrollment serve to nudge passive investors into default options designed by financial advisors (Gajewski et al., 2023). Empirical evidence shows that advice shapes both initial asset allocation decisions and the likelihood of engaging with sustainable or nature-conscious products. In a survey of private investors, 80% of respondents sought professional advice before deciding on the suitability of their own asset allocation, underscoring the perceived value of expert input (Jansen et al., 2008). Behavioural and informational patterns observed in the wider sustainable-finance literature can be directly applied to nature-specific contexts, where investors rely even more heavily on trusted intermediaries to interpret novel and technical biodiversity information.

Advisory mechanising, both human and automated, help reduce cognitive load and overcome behavioural inertia. Instruments such as auto-enrolment and default investment options are designed to address behavioural inertia and low financial literacy among individual investors by simplifying decision-making and promoting long-term savings. Empirical evidence suggests that auto-enrolled individuals often remain in default options as they trust the choices of experts (Gajewski et al., 2023). Financial literacy can strengthen this relationship as investors who better understand investment concepts are more likely to trust professional guidance (Rooh et al., 2023). By comparing the decision-making behaviours of Swedish mutual fund investors, Lofgren and Nordblom (2024) found sustainability motivated investors more likely to seek advice and make attentive decisions, compared to return motivated investors, because they understand the high level of complexity in the choices they face and often lack confidence in their own investment knowledge. The authors make several recommendations to banks and financial advisors to better support sustainability motivated investors, including tailored communication services and simplified decision-making mechanisms to better align their clients' investments with their values.

Technological innovation is reshaping the landscape of financial advice, significantly influencing how individual investors engage with nature-conscious investment opportunities. Robo-advisors typify this shift by offering algorithm-driven, cost-efficient, and accessible investment services that integrate sustainability preferences into portfolio construction. Their ability to eliminate emotional bias and provide consistent, data-driven recommendations enhances investor confidence, particularly among younger, cost-aware, and ecologically motivated individuals (Au et al., 2021). Concurrently, the emergence of green fintech-encompassing blockchain, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics-further empowers investors by improving the transparency, traceability, and credibility of ESG-related information. These technologies facilitate informed decision-making by enabling faster access to environmental impact data and personalised sustainability metrics (Macchiavello & Siri, 2020). As a result, individual investors are increasingly equipped to align their financial choices with environmental values, marking a departure from traditional advisory models, rooted in neo-classical assumptions of purely rational,

return-maximizing behaviour.

Evolving financial advisory services requires overcoming regulatory, ethical, and technical barriers to ensure fair and trustworthy access. Individual investors have heterogeneous preferences when it comes to their investment choices. Therefore, it is important to aid investors in the search for assets that meet their demands (Zwergel et al., 2019). Traditionally, advisors were only willing to allocate funds to sustainable assets such as slow-carbon-emitting companies if there were clear economic benefit in doing so (Haigh & Shapiro, 2013). Incorporating individual investor preferences into portfolio allocations is essential not only for fulfilling regulatory required fiduciary duties related to sustainability but also for mobilising capital towards long-term environmental objectives. The European Union has reinforced this approach through regulations such as the Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2017/565, which integrates sustainability considerations into investment, advisory and disclosure processes (Colaert, 2024). SFDR and the Taxonomy regulation further support the inclusion of sustainability considerations in investment decisions and have been instrumental in growing the sustainable investing sector in Europe, which now boasts assets in excess of 4 trillion EUR, proving the importance of financial advice in driving sustainable investment action (Marszk & Lechman, 2024). These regulatory shifts are highly relevant to nature-conscious investment, as they expand the advisory mandate to include biodiversity-related preferences, even where products are relatively new or unfamiliar.

4.6. Investment action (or assignment)

Investment actions refer to the concrete decisions investors undertake (such as allocating funds, adjusting portfolios, or selecting specific financial products) that translate their preferences and intentions into actual investment outcomes (Pilaj, 2017). Despite increasing awareness and positive attitudes toward sustainable investing, a persistent gap remains between investors stated preferences and their actual investment behaviour—a phenomenon widely referred to as the “green gap” (Merli et al., 2023). This gap is particularly pronounced for nature-conscious investments, where products are less familiar, information is more complex, and biodiversity outcomes are harder to evaluate. As a result, the same behavioural and informational frictions identified in the broader sustainable-finance literature are even more salient when translating nature-conscious preferences into actual investment behaviour.

Although many investors express a willingness to align their portfolios with environmental values, behavioural inertia, cognitive limitations, and structural barriers (particularly the complexity of ESG data) often prevent these intentions from translating into nature-conscious investment actions (Bazrafshan, 2023; Gevorkova et al., 2024). Research from the Swedish mutual fund market illustrates this: of the 71% who claimed they would be willing to give up some level of return for making pro-environmental investments, only 43% actually invested in such funds (Lofgren & Nordblom, 2024). Even when investors express pro-environmental preferences, perceived financial risk and uncertainty often deter them from acting, as sustainable products are seen as underperforming compared to conventional ones (Mavlutova et al., 2022). This pattern is likely to be even more pronounced for nature-conscious products, where return expectations are often more uncertain and the financial benefits less well-communicated. Thus, structural clarity and decision-relevant information become essential for enabling investors to act on their stated environmental values.

Information quality plays a key role in closing this intention-action gap. Access to high-quality financial information can mitigate these concerns, enabling less rational investors to balance sustainability goals with financial objectives. Benuzzi et al. (2024) demonstrated this through an online experiment, where participants often chose less financially attractive investments when they supported sustainability-related targets, highlighting how information can

influence value-driven decisions. This underscores the importance of clear and trustworthy labelling, as previously discussed in this paper. While ESG labels can build awareness and positive attitudes (ESMA, 2022a, 2022b) the current lack of standardisation across ESG ratings makes reliable information difficult or costly to obtain, often delaying preference-aligned decisions (Bazrafshan, 2023; Seifert et al., 2024). The EU's implementation of SFDR-aligned labels has improved investor engagement with sustainable products, in contrast to markets like the U.S., where such regulation is absent (Becker et al., 2022). These regulatory improvements are especially important for nature-conscious investment, where standardised biodiversity metrics remain limited.

Individual investors may also choose to delegate their investment decisions to professionals in order to leverage their expertise, reduce the risk of costly mistakes, and save time on managing complex financial portfolios (Jansson et al., 2014). Individuals often cannot, or do not want to, make their own investment choices. For example, in the Dutch collective pension system, beneficiaries have limited investment choices, as decisions are made by pension-fund boards and executed by fund managers (Apostolakis et al., 2016). These funds have a fiduciary duty to reflect members' sustainability preferences, as required by EU rules like MiFID, which mandate aligning investment advice with client values (Cucinelli & Soana, 2023). Other government interventions, such as tax incentives, can significantly influence individuals to hand their decision-making over to institutional actors. A survey of approximately 2000 Dutch households (CentER Savings Survey) found that 65% of households investing in tax-advantaged sustainable funds cited the incentive as a key motivator (Benijts, 2009).

Finally, financial literacy moderates the path from intention to action. Investors with higher literacy levels are more likely to engage ESG-aligned intermediaries and to trust sustainability-oriented recommendations (Cucinelli & Soana, 2023). Conversely, lower literacy increases susceptibility to cognitive biases, heightens reliance on defaults, and amplifies perceived risks associated with nature-conscious investments. Improving financial knowledge and confidence is therefore critical for enabling environmentally motivated individuals to make consistent, preference-aligned investment choices.

While individual investors increasingly express a desire to align their portfolios with environmental and sustainability values, the translation of these preferences into concrete investment action remains inconsistent. Bridging the green gap requires a holistic approach, integrating behavioural insights, financial literacy and institutional accountability into regulatory foundations, that supports both rational and value-driven investment decisions for the promotion of nature and biodiversity. This is particularly important for nature-conscious investment, where products are newer, impacts are harder to quantify, and biodiversity-related information is less standardised; as a result, the behavioural dynamics observed in the broader sustainable-finance literature are not only applicable but often amplified.

4.7. Post-investment adjustments

The investment decision-making process ends with post-investment monitoring and adjustments after the investment decision has been made (Pilaj, 2017). Post-investment behaviour, particularly portfolio rebalancing, has emerged as a critical yet underexplored dimension in sustainable finance literature. While initial investment decisions are shaped by psychological and informational factors, subsequent adjustments are influenced by a dynamic interplay of environmental shocks, regulatory developments, and evolving investor awareness.

Just like taking the initial decision to invest, many factors affect post-investment revisions. Individual investors, especially pension savers, often exhibit inertia in managing their portfolios due to the perceived complexity of financial markets (Katelouzou & Micheler, 2022; Rehman et al., 2024). This can slow the reallocation of capital toward sustainable or nature-conscious products, even when investor preferences or market incentives change. Studies examining external events show that shocks,

such as climate-related disasters, geopolitical crises, and sustainability-related news affect behaviour, prompting reassessment and portfolio rebalancing. These insights highlighting the role of financial literacy, regulatory consistency, and ESG communication in shaping long-term, nature-conscious investment strategies (Anderson & Robinson, 2019; Tang & Teoh, 2023).

Ecological and sustainable considerations are becoming increasingly significant in public discussions, with regulatory frameworks and public policy playing a pivotal role in shaping investment behaviour. Governments, acting both as regulators and institutional investors, influence market sentiment and individual choices through tax incentives and sustainability mandates (Katelouzou & Micheler, 2022). Consistent policies are important for maintaining confidence and encouraging long-term investments. Individual investors often adjust their investment decisions based on changes in regulations, especially those related to the environment. While short term changes can result in temporary variations in attitude, long term systematic change manifests itself in investment behaviour and asset reallocation (Rehman et al., 2024).

Media and information environments matter as well. Existing research shows that consuming economic news boosts financial literacy, and attention to sustainable finance news enhances understanding in that area. Moreover, increased reporting on positive sustainable finance developments can influence financial markets, encouraging more sustainable investment (Strauß et al., 2023). In an online experiment conducted on US investors, a notable increase in portfolio reallocation (approx. 11%) was observed in response to the receipt of ESG information, when compared to a control group where no such news is provided (Janz et al., 2023). The impact of sustainable finance communication on investors with greater exposure to ESG-related news is linked to higher financial literacy, and therefore more proactive investment monitoring.

Furthermore, extreme environmental events and strong beliefs about future climate risks are linked to shifts in investor behaviour, particularly portfolio rebalancing. Anderson and Robinson (2019) found that exposure to major weather events in Sweden led to greener investment choices, suggesting that increasing climate volatility may drive demand for sustainable retirement portfolios. Similarly, during geopolitical and health crises, investors tend to favour firms with strong ESG credentials, viewing them as more resilient (Tang & Teoh, 2023). These findings indicate that post-investment behaviour is shaped by psychological biases, external shocks, and regulatory changes.

As such disruptions become more frequent, they increasingly act as catalysts for reallocating capital toward sustainable assets. A well-regulated financial system built on reliable information is crucial for aligning long-term financial goals with environmental sustainability. This is particularly important for nature-conscious investment, where biodiversity risks are less visible and harder to quantify; therefore, the behavioural patterns, informational triggers, and policy mechanisms identified in broader sustainable-finance research apply directly and often more strongly to nature-conscious portfolio adjustments.

5. Future research agenda & conclusions

The reviewed studies reveal a critical information gap-sustainable attitudes among individual investors do not reliably translate into investment decisions. This is attributable to behavioural biases (Gajewski et al., 2023; Thaler & Benartzi, 2004), information asymmetries (Bazrafshan, 2023; Seifert et al., 2024) and structural constraints such as limited investor agency in pension systems (Apostolakis et al., 2016; Cucinelli & Soana, 2023). The review also highlights the critical role of financial literacy, particularly sustainable financial literacy (Filippini et al., 2024; Yucel et al., 2023), regulatory frameworks (Becker et al., 2022; Katelouzou & Micheler, 2022) and technological innovation (Faradynawati & Söderberg, 2022; Macchiavello & Siri, 2020) in enabling or constraining nature-conscious investment decisions. Importantly, this review identifies that individual investors' decisions

are shaped by a complex interplay of cognitive biases, emotional drivers and social convention (Khan et al., 2024; Rooh et al., 2023). These findings call for a more interdisciplinary approach to understanding and motivating individual investment behaviour for the promotion of biodiversity goals.

While much of the reviewed literature examines sustainable investing more broadly, this synthesis highlights a set of challenges that are uniquely salient in the context of nature-conscious investment. Unlike climate-focused or general ESG investments (where metrics, standards and financial products are comparatively mature) biodiversity related investments suffer from acute data gaps, limited product availability, and highly localised ecological impacts that are difficult for non-expert investors to interpret. These features amplify behavioural and informational barriers identified in existing studies and create distinct frictions that require tailored research attention. To mobilize private capital for nature, future research must build directly on the gaps identified in the reviewed evidence, extending them into nature-conscious investments, where practical tools remain underdeveloped.

5.1. Behavioural intervention & nudges

The existing literature on behavioural interventions in sustainable finance has largely focused on general savings behaviour and the activation of investment decisions. Behavioural work by Thaler and Benartzi (2004) introduced the concept of automatic enrolment and default options to overcome inertia in retirement savings behaviour. More recent studies have extended this to socially responsible finance, exploring how nudges such as default green options, commitment contracts and salience can influence individual investment behaviour (Gajewski et al., 2023).

In the context of nature-conscious investing however, the application of behavioural interventions remains relatively unexplored. While some work has been done to understand the role of psychological biases such as status quo bias, loss aversion and confirmation bias (Khan et al., 2024; Lofgren & Nordblom, 2024), most studies have focused on climate-related or general ESG investment. Few have tested targeted nudges designed to promote biodiversity-aligned investment decisions in settings where investors must evaluate nature-specific impacts such as species protection, habitat restoration or ecosystem service provision. The reviewed evidence therefore suggests a critical knowledge gap: existing behavioural interventions may not transfer to biodiversity-related investments, where uncertainty, time horizons and perceived personal relevance differ substantially. Building on the behavioural patterns documented in the reviewed literature, future studies should design and test nudges that specifically address biodiversity related uncertainty, such as default allocations to nature-conscious investment instruments. Future work should also address the methodological limitations of existing studies, which rely heavily on stated-preference surveys. There is a particular need for field experiments and longitudinal designs to test whether biodiversity-specific nudges translate into sustained changes in actual investment behaviour.

5.2. Financial advice and institutional intermediation

The literature reviewed in this study highlights the growing importance of financial advisors in aligning institutional investment practices with individual sustainability preferences. Regulations such as the EU's MiFID now require financial intermediaries to incorporate clients' sustainability preferences into their advisory processes (Cucinelli & Soana, 2023). This shift marks a broader view of advisor's duty, moving beyond financial returns to include environmental and social outcomes and reflects new research by Colaert (2024) which identifies investors' prioritisation of non-financial factors in investment decisions. However, the literature provides almost no evidence on how they engage with biodiversity-specific information. This gap is particularly important

because the barriers identified in prior sections (information overload, financial literacy and incentive misalignment for example) are likely to be amplified when products involve ecological outcomes that advisors themselves may not understand.

Individual nature-conscious investors expect their capital to be managed in line with sustainability values, even where this requires a trade-off with returns (Apostolakis et al., 2016; Jansson et al., 2014). However, the actual integration of these preferences into investment strategies remains inconsistent. The current study notes that many individuals delegate their investment decision-making to intermediaries due to the complexity of financial products or their own limited financial literacy, making the role of financial advice critical in bridging the green funding gap (Jansen et al., 2008). Although regulations are advancing, significant holes remain in the practical application of fiduciary duty to nature-conscious investing. First, we lack systematic research on how fiduciaries, especially in pensions and other collective schemes, interpret and implement sustainability preferences. Second, there is scant research on holding these intermediaries accountable for aligning decisions with non-financial investor preferences, highlighting a need for new evaluation frameworks. Finally, existing studies overwhelmingly focus on broad ESG definitions, paying little attention to the specific tools advisors need to integrate biodiversity impacts into portfolio construction. Given that most evidence on advisory behaviour is based on cross-sectional self-reports, new research should employ observational data, advisor-client interaction studies, and quasi-experimental methods to understand how fiduciaries handle nature-conscious preferences in real advisory settings. Future research should therefore build directly on the behaviours identified in the reviewed studies, extending them into nature-related contexts where fiduciary responsibilities, product governance and advisor competence remain poorly defined.

5.3. Nature-labels and financial products

The literature reviewed in this study highlights the growing reliance of individual investors on simplified labels to guide investment decisions. These labels can make it difficult for investors to identify products that specifically support biodiversity outcomes (Assaf et al., 2024; Becker et al., 2022; ESMA, 2022a, 2022b). At the same time, there is increasing recognition of the need to integrate ecological data into financial decision-making (Gerber & Iacona, 2024). Efforts such as the EU Taxonomy and SFDR have begun to standardise sustainability disclosures, but biodiversity-specific data remains under used and poorly translated into salient formats for individual investors to interpret (Zadek et al., 2021). This disconnect limits the ability of individual investors to assess the nature-related risks and opportunities associated with their investment choices. Ecological data is complex, unstructured and not specifically tailored to financial decision-making. There is also a lack of investment vehicles that explicitly incorporate biodiversity metrics into their design, creating barriers for non-expert investors.

As such, future research must be interdisciplinary and collaborate with ecologists, data-scientists and financial analysts to convert biodiversity data into decision-useful indicators. Future work should build on the EU Ecolabel and other taxonomy aligned frameworks to design and test biodiversity-specific labels, that clearly indicate the impact of financial products on nature. Methodologically, current findings rest largely on hypothetical choice experiments; future studies should incorporate behavioural tracking and product-level impact data to test how investors engage with biodiversity-specific labels in real markets. Furthermore, advancing the integration of verifiable biodiversity data into the technological tools used by individual investors and their advisors can support more personalised, nature-conscious investment strategies. Drawing on these insights, future research must investigate how investors interpret biodiversity information differently from general ESG labels, and test whether nature-specific labels can reduce cognitive load and enable preference-aligned decision-making.

In conclusion, this review exposes a critical disconnect between the

sustainable values of individual investors and their financial actions, driven by behavioural biases and structural barriers. The review demonstrates that although sustainable investing is well studied, the evidence base becomes extremely thin when narrowed to biodiversity-related decisions, with less than 1% of studies focused on nature-conscious investments. To mobilize essential private capital for nature, an interdisciplinary research agenda is urgently needed-one that develops biodiversity-specific behavioural interventions, strengthens understanding of how advisors operationalise nature-conscious preferences, and creates intelligible biodiversity-labelled financial labels and products. Addressing these gaps is essential for translating stated investor preferences into concrete capital flows capable of supporting meaningful biodiversity outcomes.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Ciara Clohessy: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Vasilis Grigoriadis:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Fergal O’Brien:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **John Garvey:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Funding

Appendix

This appendix provides additional information on the methodology use to identify literature for this review paper. The full systematic review procedure can be found in the pre-published protocol (Clohessy et al., 2025).

We employed the PICO framework, a commonly used model in medicine for structuring clinical questions, to breakdown the key components required (Schardt, et al., 2007).

- Problem: How to promote greater investment in nature-based solutions & biodiversity.
 - Intervention: Motivating retail/individual investors by activating their behavioural tendencies.
 - Control: The primary markets/instruments within which retail investors currently operate.
 - Outcomes (expected): Behavioural biases/Bottlenecks.
- From this analysis we derived several secondary research questions:

1. How does the behavioural approach of individual investors to pension planning impact nature conscious investment?
2. How will changing individual investor behaviour in the savings market impact green investment?
3. How will changing technology affect individual investors approach to Nature Based Finance?
4. How does investors attitudes to risk/return affect their approach to green solutions?

(a) Search Strings

Key words associated with each element of the PICO question breakdown were used to form the search string. Using this string, a structured search was carried out on key databases (Scopus, Web of Science and Google Scholar).

Problem	Intervention	Control	Outcome
"Nature Positive Investment"	"Individual investor"	"Pension Funds"	"Bottlenecks"
"Nature Finance"	"Pensioneer"	"Funds"	"Barriers"
"Green Investment"	"Retail investors"	"Savings Market"	"Policy"
"Ecosystem Investment"	"Private investor"	"Investment Funds"	"Quotas"
"Nature Based Finance"	"Risk adverse investor"	"Online Trading Platforms"	"Technology"
"Biodiversity"	"Green Investor"	"Bond Market"	"Information"
"ESG Investment"	"Impact Investor"	"Hedge Fund"	"Risk"
"Sustainable Finance"		"ESG Fund"	"Return"
"Climate Action Investment"		"Pensions"	"Behavioural Bias"
			"Inertia"

The key words were then combined using the Boolean operators “OR” and “AND” to extract literature that combines all terms for each of the key components of the research question as follows:

Search String = “Problem₁” OR “Problem₂” OR ... “Problem_n” AND “Intervention₁” OR “Intervention₂” OR ... “Intervention_n” AND “Control₁” OR “Control₂” OR ... “Control_n” AND “Outcome₁” OR “Outcome₂” OR ... “Outcome_n”

Minor adaptations were made to the search string format as required for each database, but the terms remained constant for each search conducted.

(b) Screening & Inclusion Criteria

This review protocol follows the example set out by (Grigoriadis et al., 2023) in employing the guidelines of PRISMA-P (preferred reporting items for systematic review and meta-analysis protocols), to organise and document the review method. Following the 17-item checklist laid out in the PRISMA protocol will act as a safe-guard against subjectivity in the review during the decision-making process (Moher & al., 2015) (Grigoriadis, et al., 2023).

The first stage of screening assessed each item brought forward for review on a title and abstract level. Each item was reviewed in line with the PICO criteria, based on its relevance to key components of the research. Each PICO element was equally weighted in the inclusion/exclusion decision, whereby the element was assigned a value between 0 and 1. Additionally, items were assigned a binary value 0 or 1 based on whether or not they were in-date. For the purpose of this review, in-date is defined as texts published from 2000 onwards. Each PICO element was assessed on a series of subcategories which will be assigned a value (summing to a maximum of 1) based on their relevance to the research. They are as follows:

Problem	<i>How to promote greater investment in nature-based solutions & biodiversity</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nature Based Finance • Green Investment • Biodiversity • ESG • Climate Action 	
Intervention	<i>Motivating retail/individual Investors by activating their behavioural tendencies</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Retail/Individual Investors 	
Control	<i>The primary markets/instruments within which retail investors currently operate</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pension/ Savings Market 	
Outcomes	<i>Behavioural biases/Bottlenecks</i>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Investor Behaviour • Bottlenecks/Barriers • Investment Characteristics 	

In order to overcome bias, a second review was carried out using the same methodology by an independent reviewer. Any disagreements between the reviews were deferred to a third party to decide on inclusion/exclusion. We tested against a range of tolerance levels at which a document should be included. We found, as expected, the higher the tolerance level, the lower the number of papers included. The result of this screening process is discussed in section 3 above.

Data availability statement

No data generated.

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